

ADOPTION OF E-LEARNING IN INDIA- TRENDS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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ABSTRACT

Countries all over the world are focusing on the continuous online delivery of the education in this pandemic condition. For this all stakeholders of the education need to play an important role, as learning can never be put on hold. All strata of education system are taking digital initiatives from kindergarten to research level so that the teaching-learning process continues. Online education is prevalent in all academic institutions in the world in various modes. Emergence of new technologies, universal adoption of World Wide Web, training requirement of future workforce that will be essentially based on technology is the basis of development of new framework in education system. MHRD has already taken many initiatives to enhance learning by various digital platforms for academic fraternity. In the coming years, digital learning is going to become indispensable in our education system.

Keywords : E-learning, Digital technologies, Higher education, Government policies

Introduction

In the present situation with the eruption of Covid-19 all across the world, various prudent and defensive steps are being taken to encounter this universal pandemic. It was the foremost need of shutting down all schools, universities, workplaces, events to check the spreading of this novel virus. Teaching-Learning process was envisioned to be held back at this time to considerable duration of time. However, technology came to our rescue and assisted us in continuing with learning process through various means available online.

Technology plays a great role in learning process. It has been rightly mentioned that learning should not stop under any catastrophe. Information and Communication Technology is a great coordinator and facilitator for the process of e-learning, it assisted in maintaining the process of teaching-learning all in one piece at this critical time. Diversified digital platforms enabled with ICT tools are available for educators, students, research scholars and everyone who is keen to

learn 24×7. All these tools can be accessed at flexible timings and provide constant learning whenever desired at comfortable pace. UGC, India has organized, prepared and shared assorted links available online on various platforms that can be easily accessed by all academic members, students, faculties, researchers in the form of audio, video or text.

E-Learning as the need of the hour

The term online-learning can be defined as the application and integration of electronic based media, education technology and also ICT in online education. Online learning or *e-learning* is described as a learning managed by means of electronic media, generally supported by the online network (Oxford Learner's Dictionary). The success of online learning relies on the self-motivation of individuals to learn productively. E-learning industry is economically and reasonably substantial. Advancements in the areas of web based and multimedia technologies are the elemental facilitator of e-learning. The industry has five key factors like-

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consultative, teaching-learning content, various technologies, services and support. Online learning enhances distance learning programmes and learning with flexibility. It can also help in traditional classroom teaching in unification with web based teaching and learning.

E-learning has numerous advantages, as in it helps in saving time and expenditure or the probability of learning anytime and anywhere. Many students accept that this type of learning is convenient for them to pursue various degrees at higher level. A great majority out of these students are intrigued to pursue methods which allow them self-paced learning in flexible environment. Furthermore, in non-synchronous digital learning classes, students are not restricted to any time, they can simply log in whenever they feel like and complete their assigned tasks. After so many benefits still, a small section of teachers considers it tough to keep their students occupied in an online-learning class. One of the reasons could be the lack of face-to-face interaction like that in a traditional class, which develops and affects various affective domains.

Future Trends of E-Learning

E-Learning is an emerging methodology of modern education. It is gradually growing very fast for last two decades in the education sector. All the university, schools and companies started offering online courses to satisfy the student needs, and to improve employee effectiveness. With the development of technology, India has witnessed an enhanced acceptance of online education over a period of few years. Many students and working professionals have joined different e-learning platforms in the past few years in order to enhance their skills. And, looking at trends, the number of people adopting online education platforms is expected to increase significantly in the near future.

- **Adaptive Learning**

Adaptive learning is a style of education where resources, activities, projects, and assignments are tailored to each student's individual needs. In the context of eLearning, the implementation of adaptive learning is usually performed by way of established algorithms and assessments, as opposed to the potentially arbitrary

determinations of teachers themselves.

Thus far, adaptive learning has been largely experimental, with companies and competitors having spent the past couple of years working out the kinks and engaging in small-scale execution. As eLearning continues to develop, the experiments will end and the widespread adoption will begin. Already, the major eLearning platforms are offering adaptive learning services, and there's no reason that the trend won't continue for the foreseeable future.

- **Social Learning**

Social learning takes the base components of human interaction and group dynamics and applies them to the modern technological age. Online forums, class-wide chatrooms, file-sharing platforms – with social learning in the electronic space, collaboration has never been more productive, efficient, and seamless. Now, teammates can offer insight and support from anywhere, whether it be their classroom, their homes, or their nearby coffeeshops.

As social learning applications continue to develop, more and more collaborative tools will likely enter the fray for market dominance. What's more is that, outside of individual classrooms and group project scenarios, social learning as a whole could grow to become the spine of school-wide curriculums everywhere.

- **Video learning**

Although it's a bit of a generalization, they say that there are three types of learners – visual, auditory, and kinesthetics – that excel best in education when faced with videos, vocals, and practical demonstrations, respectively. For many years, despite this dichotomy, auditory learners were the only group properly served by the standard lecture/note-taking classroom format. With the advent of eLearning, that's no longer the case, with video learning becoming more and more of a fixture in classrooms everywhere.

From video-based lectures to instructional videos, video learning has certainly come a long way from the shared-classroom televisions of old. Today, and going forward, there is nary an application that cannot be improved by the use of video learning. As such, there's no

reason to expect a backslide anytime soon.

- **Artificial Intelligence**

It's safe to say that artificial intelligence, or AI, has surpassed its original reputation of being the evil impetus. Beyond simple smartphone commands, AI has found a use in the context of eLearning. Backing up the concepts behind adaptive learning, AI is not only able to guide students through courses, but it can also help inform learning predictions and on-the-fly personalization. The potential applications for this currently seem limitless, considering the presence of AI in several industries outside of education. Within, however, consumers and instructors alike can expect more and more sophistication, with more flexibility permitted when it comes to alternative learning styles and needs.

- **Microlearning**

It's common sense that many students, regardless of their age, may be daunted at the prospect of large, multi-phase projects. Those students, as well as collaborative classrooms everywhere, have found much greater successful by breaking up projects, lessons, and other learning materials into manageable chunks. These so-called chunks may manifest as video lectures, readable text, interactive activities, to name just a few applications.

Otherwise known as microlearning, instructors have found that lessons, in addition to online modules, yield greater and faster retention when, for example, a 2-hour long lesson is broken up into 4 30-minute long sessions. Microlearning is indicative of a trend that goes beyond eLearning itself, and into the realm of traditional classroom spaces. As such, it's clear that the common implementation of microlearning is not yet complete.

- **Gamification**

It doesn't matter whether you're five years old or fifty, learning is always more interesting, not to mention more digestible, when it's fun. Referred to as gamification, this facet of eLearning attempts to make education fun!

It isn't all about fun and games, however, as there are proven benefits surrounding the initiation of games following the introduction or review of lessons. First off, it can provide immediate application of, and interaction

with, the material. When understanding is up, so too is engagement, retention, grades, and overall classroom happiness. Given the large swath of positive results, there's no reason that game-based learning solutions will not continue to be implemented in classrooms, both digital and physical, for the foreseeable future. Moreover, when it comes to the somewhat impersonal nature of eLearning in particular, gamification of the industry is not just welcomed, it's ideal.

- **Mobile Learning**

Although not strictly a part of what comprises 'traditional' eLearning, the evolution of mobile learning, or m-Learning, is certainly an appropriate trend to consider. Not too long ago, the concept of doing anything on your mobile device beyond simple phone calls and 8-bit games was a pipe dream. Fast forward to today, just about everything is possible, and everyone appreciates the ability to do things while on-the-go.

When it comes to m-Learning, however, there is still a slight bit of way to go before it becomes fully viable. The past couple of years have been very kind to it, in that respect, with phone-based language-learning applications coming to the fore. While it's a decent step, m-Learning architectures still need to find ways to embrace the same learning facets trends that eLearning managed to do before it can become widespread and commonplace. That said, in the future, there's no doubt that m-Learning will grow to be huge.

- **Learning Management Systems**

In many collaborative environments and workplaces, employers and managers commonly implement what is known as a content management system, or CMS, to create and store digital content. Recently, this concept has expanded into the world of eLearning. With the advent of learning management systems (LMS), instructors and other eLearning practitioners are able to develop, document, and administer the courses and curriculums that are produced.

Considering the behind-the-scenes nature of LMSs, it has become easier than ever to simultaneously plan ahead and course-correct. In either case, this sort of content curation works is permitted by way of an LMS user's ability to share information and integrate materials

at the last minute. As modern forms of learning, and eLearning in particular, become more and more digitized and supported, the availability of an LMS will make lesson planning and management a breeze, thus doing away with the old analogue methods for good. As such, LMSs are here to stay.

Conclusion :

In today's global world, there are no strict personal, cultural and educational boundaries. Online education leads to lifelong learning anytime and anywhere that becomes helpful for the students. Also it is a tremendous way to increase the academic and professional competency by the educators and researchers by creating open educational resources for all to access. Digital transformation has helped to convert educators into producer and architect of knowledge. Every online education effort has given the academicians the time for learning and teaching simultaneously. Michael Allen has aptly said, "There are no refunds; learners cannot get their time back if we waste it." So it is better to continue with teaching-learning with the help of technology integrated in our future education and teaching approaches.

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